

The Influence of Using Instagram on EFL Learners' Critical Thinking in Language Institutes

Mahdi Zalani, Nouroddin Yousofi

This study examined the influence of using Instagram on EFL learners' critical thinking in language institutes. The participants were 68 students studying English at language institutes. Two equal groups were formed as experimental and control. As the pretest, California Critical Thinking Skills Test and California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory were utilised. Afterward, the experimental group were taught in class and via Instagram, while the control group were taught only in class without using Instagram. The treatment lasted for 12 weeks. Then the posttest by using the same aforementioned tests was administered. The two groups got nearly the same scores on the pretest, but, their performances on the posttest were different and the experimental group performed better than the control group.

Key words: *Critical Thinking, Instagram, Language Institutes, MALL, Language Learning.*

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.14925437

1. INTRODUCTION

Thompson (2015) asserted that mobile learning experience offers the convenience of distance or online learning. Tools offered by social media can be utilised in order to deliver content and information. By Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) Social Networking Systems (SNS) can be brought into the class which enables learners to interact with an authentic L2 community outside the formal context of education. Technology and critical thinking are the two most important factors of modern education. The utilisation of technology like online learning by using digital platforms could improve learners' critical thinking and develop their reasoning, problem-solving, and decision making (Lopez-Perez, 2011); it could also foster collaboration among learners by activities such as online discussions (Carmichael & Farrel, 2012; Foo & Quek, 2019).

To the best of our knowledge, in the available literature Instagram has never been utilized in order to develop EFL learners' critical thinking skills in language institutes. Therefore, with the aim of filling the lacuna, one question should be answered:

Does any significant difference exist between critical thinking proficiency of EFL learners who receive instructions in class and via Instagram and EFL learners who receive instructions only in class without using Instagram?

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants

Sixty-eight students of English language institutes located in Iran with a limited age range (20 to 22 years old) including 34 females and 34 males took parts in this research. They were selected through purposive sampling and shared the same L1 which was Persian. Two equal groups as control and experimental were formed.

2.2. Instrumentation

2.2.1. Homogeneity test

The learners' proficiency in English was checked by administering *DIALANG*. *DIALANG* assesses reading, listening, writing, grammar, and vocabulary. *DIALANG* tests learners' proficiency level in 14 European languages. It is only utilised as a diagnosis test and its usage for purposes other than diagnosis is rejected by its inventors. *DIALANG* provides its users with feedback and reviews their answers to the test items. Users' proficiency level is determined based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Based on CEFR, levels of proficiency are categorized as A1 (Breakthrough), A2 (Wastage), B1 (Threshold), B2 (Vantage), C1 (Effective Operational Proficiency), and C2 (Mastery). The participants were asked to consult <https://dialangweb.lancaster.ac.uk> and take the test. They were required to send the results to the teacher via e-mail. Then the learners were assigned to two equal groups as experimental and control based on their scores on *DIALANG*.

2.2.2. California critical thinking skills test

This test is owned and administered by Insight Assessment and available at www.insightassessment.com. There are 34 multiple-choice items which include 8 distinctive subscales for assessing critical thinking. The subscales are: Numeracy, Deductive Reasoning, Inductive Reasoning, Explanation, Evaluation, Inference, Interpretation, and Analysis. Scores are made based on a propriety formula and range from low to non-manifested, weak development, moderate development, strong development, and superior development. As a part of the pretest and posttest, the test was administered with the aim of evaluating the participants' improvement and figuring out which group could progress more significantly. By comparing the learners' performances on the pretest and posttest, the researchers could discover which group's treatment was more effective.

2.2.3. California critical thinking disposition inventory

This test is owned and administered by Insight Assessment and available at www.insightassessment.com. There are 75 statements in it and should be responded based on a 6-point Likert scale. The test assesses individuals' dispositions toward critical thinking. Seven distinctive subscales are included in this test: Maturity of Judgement, Inquisitiveness, Confidence in Reasoning, Systematicity, Open-Mindedness, Analyticity, and Truth Seeking. The scores range from 5 to 60 for each subscale. As a part of the pretest and posttest, the test was administered with the aim of evaluating the participants' improvement and figuring out which group could progress more significantly. By comparing the learners' performances on the pretest and posttest, the researchers could discover which group's treatment was more effective.

2.2.4. Pretest

California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) and California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) were administered online. The participants were required to consult www.insightassessment.com and take the tests. The participants sent the tests results to their teacher via e-mail.

2.2.5. Educational materials and instructions

2.2.5.1. Control group

The control group received instructions for critical thinking in class without using Instagram. They were studying their coursebooks during the semester which were *Viewpoint (2)* and *Oxford Word Skills (Advanced)*. Moreover, *Halpern (2014)*, *Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking* and *Corey (2010)*, *Audio Production and Critical Listening* were taught in addition to the coursebooks. The treatment lasted for 12 weeks each week for two sessions and each session for two hours. The researchers prepared summaries of each unit of the books and presented them during 30 minutes in each session. The 30-minute-instruction was delivered at the beginning of each session and the rest of time (90 minutes) was devoted to teaching the coursebooks.

2.2.5.2. Experimental group

The experimental group studied *Viewpoint (2)* and *Oxford Word Skills (Advanced)* as their coursebooks. Moreover, *Halpern (2014)*, *Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking* and *Corey (2010)*, *Audio Production and Critical Listening* were taught in addition to the coursebooks. The treatment lasted for 12 weeks each week for two sessions and each session for two hours. The researchers prepared summaries of each unit of the books and presented them during 30 minutes in each session. The 30-minute-instruction was delivered at the beginning of each session and the rest of time (90 minutes) was devoted to teaching the coursebooks. The experimental group, who were all Instagram users, were asked to view @euronews, @bbc, @voa, @cnn, @reuters, @foxnews, and @france24_en on Instagram daily with the aim of watching videos about political and social subjects presented in the accounts and analysing the analyses presented there. An important domestic and foreign policy issue that the participants had viewed some contents about prior to the upcoming session would become the subject of classroom discussion. The teacher and all the students would participate in the discussions to identify the strategies used for making and presenting the content in the accounts to have the most influential impact on the audiences' mind. The teacher made use of the summaries of the books which were taught each session to help students improve their critical thinking. Additionally, an Instagram account was created by the teacher and the posts, reels, and stories adopted from some Instagram accounts available in Instagram Explore were re-shared there. The experimental group were required to follow the account and participate in the process and interact with their peers and the researchers. The content was mostly adopted from the accounts active in social and political news and issues but they were not as famous as the ones mentioned earlier. So, this was not easy for the participants to find these accounts and view what they presented. The teacher eased the process of finding new content by searching and obtaining these materials and presenting them in the account of the class. The teacher would upload questions in stories and the learners were required to answer the questions by replying the stories. The teacher would read all the messages received and answer them. The responses were also uploaded as stories until all the participants could see their classmates' responses and the teacher's explanations. The teacher also made some videos using *Inshot* application. In this videos the teacher provided some explanations on the videos which were presented in @euronews, @bbc, @voa, @cnn, @reuters, @foxnews, and @france24_en and the account of the class. This was a way of online learning where students could see their teacher explaining critical thinking instructions in a context other than classroom setting. The teacher also held meetings via Instagram Live and the learners could interact with their teacher and peers by talking in the Live via their cameras or

commenting on the Live while others were speaking. The teacher adopted turn taking strategy and each session was devoted to letting three students attend the Live by their cameras on and interacting with their teacher. The comments under each Instagram Post uploaded in the classroom account was also an opportunity for having discussions. Everybody was supposed to write his/her comments regarding the uploaded post and then the interactions among the users and the teacher would begin.

2.2.6. Posttest

At the end of the treatments, California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) and California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) were administered online. The participants were required to consult www.insightassessment.com and take the tests. The participants sent the tests results to their teacher via e-mail.

2.3. Procedure

For doing this research *Nonrandomized Control Group, Pretest-Posttest design* (Ary et al., 2019) was employed. Sixty-eight students of language institutes in Iran with a limited age range (20 to 22 years old) including 34 males and 34 females participated in this study. They were selected through purposive sampling and shared the same L1 which was Persian. Based on their scores on *DIALANG*, two equal groups were formed as experimental and control. Then as the pretest, California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) and California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) were administered online. The participants were required to consult www.insightassessment.com and take the tests. The participants sent the tests results to their teacher via e-mail. The control group received instructions for critical thinking in class without using Instagram. They were studying their coursebooks during the semester which were *Viewpoint (2)* and *Oxford Word Skills (Advanced)*. Moreover, *Halpern (2014), Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking* and *Corey (2010), Audio Production and Critical Listening* were taught in addition to the coursebooks. The treatment lasted for 12 weeks each week for two sessions and each session for two hours. The researchers prepared summaries of each unit of the books and presented them during 30 minutes in each session. The 30-minute-instruction was delivered at the beginning of each session and the rest of time (90 minutes) was devoted to teaching the coursebooks. The experimental group studied *Viewpoint (2)* and *Oxford Word Skills (Advanced)* as their coursebooks. Moreover, *Halpern (2014), Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking* and *Corey (2010), Audio Production and Critical Listening* were taught in addition to the coursebooks. The treatment lasted for 12 weeks each week for two sessions and each session for two hours. The researchers prepared summaries of each unit of the books and presented them during 30 minutes in each session. The 30-minute-instruction was delivered at the beginning of each session and the rest of time (90 minutes) was devoted to teaching the coursebooks. The experimental group, who were all Instagram users, were asked to view @euronews, @bbc, @voa, @cnn, @reuters, @foxnews, and @france24_en on Instagram daily with the aim of watching videos about political and social subjects presented in the accounts and analysing the analyses presented there. An important domestic and foreign policy issue that the participants had viewed some contents about prior to the upcoming session would become the subject of classroom discussion. The teacher and all the students would participate in the discussions to identify the strategies used for making and presenting the content in the accounts to have the most influential impact on the audiences' mind. The teacher made use of the summaries of the books which were taught each session to help students improve their critical thinking. Additionally, an Instagram account was created by the teacher and the posts, reels, and stories adopted from some Instagram accounts available in Instagram Explore were re-shared there. The experimental group were required to follow the account and participate in the process and interact with their peers and the researchers. The content was mostly adopted from the accounts active in social and political news and issues but they were not as famous as the ones mentioned earlier. So, this was not easy for the participants to find these accounts and view what they presented. The teacher eased the process of finding new content by searching and obtaining these materials and presenting them in the account of the class. The teacher would upload questions in stories and the learners were required to answer the questions by replying the stories. The teacher would read all the messages received and answer them. The responses were also uploaded as stories until all the participants could see their classmates' responses and the teacher's explanations. The teacher also made some videos using *Inshot* application. In this videos the teacher provided some explanations on the videos which were presented in @euronews, @bbc, @voa, @cnn, @reuters, @foxnews, and @france24_en and the account of the class. This was a way of online learning where students could see their teacher explaining critical thinking instructions in a context other than classroom setting. The teacher also held meetings via Instagram Live and the learners could interact with their teacher and peers by talking in the Live via their cameras or commenting on the Live while others were speaking. The teacher adopted a turn taking strategy and each session was devoted to letting three students attend the Live by their cameras on and interacting with their teacher. The comments under each Instagram Post uploaded in the classroom account was also an opportunity for having discussions. Everybody was supposed to write his/her comments regarding the uploaded post and then the interactions among the users and the teacher would begin. After the treatments ended, California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) and California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) were administered online. The participants were required to consult www.insightassessment.com and take the tests. The participants sent the tests results to their teacher via e-mail.

2.4. Data analysis

The teacher was in charge of analysing the data. For answering the research question, first, the tests' descriptive statistics were calculated for both groups. Then the *Independent Samples t-test* and *Paired Sample t-test* were run to determine the effectiveness of using Instagram on EFL learners' critical thinking. In this study, group membership was the independent variable with two levels (i.e. experimental and control) and the learners' scores on the posttest were the dependent variable; additionally, the learners' scores on the pretest were considered as the covariate to partial out their background knowledge of the educational materials. The difference scores of the two groups on (CCTST) and (CCTDI) were evaluated employing the *Independent Samples t-test* and analysis of variance (ANOVA) which were calculated by utilising the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Research question

The question this research tried to answer was "Does any significant difference exist between critical thinking proficiency of EFL learners who receive instructions in class and via Instagram and EFL learners who receive instructions only in class without using Instagram?". As a part of the pretest (CCTST) was utilised to assess the participants' critical thinking skills. Table 1 represents the descriptive statistics of the two groups' marks on CCTST (pretest).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Experimental and Control Groups' CCTST (Pretest) Scores

CCTST	Group	N	Mean	SD
Total Score	Exp Group	34	11.30	2.17
	Con Group	34	11.29	2.23
Analysis	Exp Group	34	3.70	1.80
	Con Group	34	3.90	1.22
Evaluation	Exp Group	34	4.20	1.14
	Con Group	34	4.58	1.88
Inference	Exp Group	34	3.40	1.37
	Con Group	34	2.81	.84

By comparing the total scores of both groups, it could be inferred that the experimental group ($M=11.30$) scored slightly higher on CCTST (pretest) than the control group ($M=11.29$). After administering the pretest, the two groups received their treatments and then the posttest was administered. Table 2 represents the descriptive statistics of the two groups' marks on CCTST (posttest).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Experimental and Control Groups' CCTST (Posttest) Scores

CCTST	Group	N	Mean	SD
Total Score	Exp Group	34	13.10	2.37
	Con Group	34	11.33	2.20
Analysis	Exp Group	34	4.95	1.71
	Con Group	34	3.95	.91
Evaluation	Exp Group	34	4.70	1.57
	Con Group	34	4.53	2.08
Inference	Exp Group	34	3.45	1.18
	Con Group	34	2.85	.65

To examine the statistical differences between the two groups' marks on CCTST (pretest and posttest), the *Independent Samples t-test* was employed. Table 3 represents the results of the *Independent Samples t-test*.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of the Independent Samples t-test for the Experimental and Control Groups' CCTST Scores

CCTST	Exp-Con Group	t	p
-------	---------------	---	---

Total Score	Pretest	.013	.990	
Posttest		2.089	.045	
Analysis	Pretest			
Posttest		2.269	.030	-.519 .610
Evaluation	Pretest			
Posttest		.380	.699	-.940 .360
Inference	Pretest			
Posttest			.930	1.798 .077 .358

It is obvious that the *Total Score* and the *Analysis* subscale mark of the experimental group were substantially greater than the control group on the CCTST (posttest), while the two groups' performances on the CCTST (pretest), in terms of the *Total Score* and all the subscales were not substantially different.

To determine the statistical difference between the pretest and posttest marks of the experimental group, the *Paired Samples t-test* was employed. Table 4 represents the descriptive statistics of the *Paired Samples t-test*.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of the Paired Samples t-test for the Experimental and Control Groups' CCTST Scores

CCTST	Pretest-Posttest	t	p
Total Score	Experimental-2.779		.020
Control	-0.300.767		
Analysis	Experimental-2.697.010		
Control	-.369 .696		
Evaluation	Experimental	-2.240	.031
Control	.365.699		
Inference	Experimental	1.088	.290
Control	-.400.731		

As represented in Table 4, the statistical difference for the control group's pretest and posttest marks was assessed by running the *Paired Samples t-test* for the *Total Score* and the subscale marks of CCTSTS. No significant difference was found for *Total Score* of CCTST ($t = -.300$; $p = .767 > .05$), the subscale score of *Analysis* ($t = -.369$; $p = .696 > .05$); the subscale score of *Evaluation* ($t = .365$; $p = .699 > .05$); and the subscale score of *Inference* ($t = -.400$; $p = .731 > .05$) as the results of the *Paired Samples t-test* proved. The statistical difference for the experimental group's pretest and posttest scores was assessed, too. Based on the results of the *Paired Samples t-test* for the *Total Score* and the subscale scores of CCTST, there were substantial differences for the *Total Score* ($t = -2.779$; $p = .020 < .05$), the subscale of *Analysis* ($t = -2.697$; $p = .010 < .05$), *Evaluation* ($t = -2.240$; $p = .031 < .05$), and *Inference* ($t = 1.088$; $p = .290 < .05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that using Instagram positively influenced the experimental group's critical thinking skills and they got better scores on the posttest in comparison with the control group.

As the other part of the pretest and to examine the participants' critical thinking dispositions, (CCTDI) was also administered. Table 5 represents the descriptive statistics of the experimental and control groups' scores on CCTDI (pretest).

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of the Experimental and Control Groups' CCTDI (Pretest) Scores

Group	NXsd	t	df	p
Experimental	34 239.01	19.966	.340	54 .729
Control	34237.94	21.260	.340	54 .729

As shown in Table 5, the experimental group's critical thinking dispositions were slightly higher in comparison with the control group. Nevertheless, the total critical thinking scores of the two groups were not substantially different ($t = .340$; $p = .729 > .05$). Thus, it can be inferred that the two groups had similar critical thinking dispositions.

No substantial difference was seen between the marks of the two groups on the CCTDI (pretest). To examine the difference between the two groups' marks on the pretest and posttest, the OneWay Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for non-related measurements was used. Table 6 represents descriptive statistics of the pretest-posttest difference scores.

Table 6. Pretest-Posttest CCTDI Difference Score of the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	X	sd
Experimental	34	17.95	15.002
Control	34	5.100	23.007

As shown in Table 6, critical thinking dispositions' difference mark for the experimental and control groups were $X=17.95$ and $X=5.100$ respectively. The experimental group's difference mark was greater. To ensure that the difference between the two groups' critical thinking disposition scores was significant, ANOVA was run and Table 7 represents its results.

Table 7. Variance Analysis of Difference Scores for the Experimental and Control Groups on CCTDI Pretest and Posttest

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Score	F	p
Between Groups	2351.862	1		2351.862	7.020
Within Groups	20601.056	51		384.011	
Total	22952.918	52			

Based on the descriptive statistics presented in Table 7, a substantial difference was observed in terms of the two groups' pretest-posttest difference scores in critical thinking dispositions ($F=7.020$, $p < .05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that using Instagram positively influenced the experimental group's critical thinking dispositions. Table 8 represents the differences between the experimental and control groups' marks in terms of the subscales of CCTDI.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics of the Pretest-Posttest Difference Scores for the Subscales of CCTDI

Subscales	Group	N	X	sd	t	df	p
Analyticity	Experimental	34	3.910	4.420	3.111	51	.040
	Control	34	.880	4.260			
Open-Mindedness	Experimental	34	4.410	4.597	3.383	51	.010
	Control	34	-.280	5.701			
Inquisitiveness	Experimental	34	3.86	4.876	3.477	51	.036
	Control	34	1.52	4.969			
Self-Confidence	Experimental	34	4.69	8.201	3.021	51	.039
	Control	34	1.95	9.101			
Truth-Seeking	Experimental	34	5.39	7.301	3.225	51	.019
	Control	34	1.41	7.011			
Systematicity	Experimental	34	3.74	8.995	3.095	51	.043
	Control	34	.850	6.892			

As shown in Table 8, the two groups' critical thinking dispositions substantially differed at all the subscales of CCTDI and the experimental group got higher scores. Thus, it can be concluded that using Instagram positively influenced critical thinking dispositions of the experimental group and they improved more than the control group.

4. DISCUSSION

This research aimed to examine the influence of using Instagram on EFL learners' critical thinking in language institutes. The question that this study tried to answer was "Does any significant difference exist between critical thinking proficiency of EFL learners who receive instructions in class and via Instagram and EFL learners who receive instructions only in class without using Instagram?". The two groups' close mean scores on the pretest showed their same level of proficiency in critical thinking. But, on the posttest they had different mean scores which can be considered as the evidence supporting the superiority of the instructions that were taught to the experimental group. The experimental group's critical thinking proficiency improved significantly and they performed more successfully on the posttest compared with their counterparts in the control group. Comparing the two marks of the control group, it could be inferred that their performance slightly improved on the posttest. Perhaps they had practiced critical thinking skills independently after taking the pretest and became interested. Moreover, attending their classes and being taught based on a traditional approach certainly contributed to their improvement. Additionally, taking the

pretest helped them gain experience and consequently perform better on the posttest. Even though there are many schools of thought around critical thinking, still some controversies exist about whether critical thinking is a general or domain-specific skill. Most scholars working in the field of critical thinking highlight the significance of background knowledge (Moore, 2011; Ventura et al., 2017; Willingham, 2007). Nevertheless, other researchers believe that critical thinking can be improved generally (Halpern, 2014). Saleh (2019) conducted a study and concluded that students' critical thinking must be stimulated. In another study, Pnevmatikos (2019) concluded that students' critical thinking skills must be promoted. Despite the cognitive aspect of critical thinking, Ku (2009) added an additional aspect to it and believed that critical thinking ability relies on one's strong intention and initiative to engage in related mental processes. In fact, in addition to engaging in cognitive skills, a critical thinker must strongly intend to identify the significance of good thinking and be innovative to look for better judgements. Using multimedia learning materials enhances students' critical thinking ability and consequently improves their problem solving skills (Facione, 2013). The utilisation of technology like online learning by using digital platforms could improve learners' critical thinking and develop their reasoning, problem-solving, and decision making (Lopez-Perez, 2011); it could also foster collaboration among learners by activities such as online discussions (Carmichael & Farrel, 2012; Foo & Quek, 2019). In this study, we adopted the explicit approach for teaching critical thinking. Utilising Instagram eased the teaching practice since the political and social analyses presented in Instagram were utilised to uncover the meaning embedded in them. The content presented in Instagram was implicit in nature but utilised for the explicit teaching of critical thinking as a result of the critical thinking instructions delivered by the teacher. The results of our study proved the effectiveness of the explicit approach of teaching critical thinking. As shown in the "Results" of this study, utilising Instagram improved the experimental group's critical thinking skills and dispositions. Thus, Instagram can be utilised as a means for delivering critical thinking instructions and practicing it as well as motivating and encouraging learners to think critically.

5. CONCLUSION

Nowadays people encounter complex social and political issues all the time and for solving problems and making wise decisions need critical thinking (Bagheri, 2015; Zarrinabadi et al., 2021). Thus, integrating critical thinking instructions in pedagogical courses is crucial for all the societies in the world. The period of time during which we conducted our study was short and the study was also restricted to the context of language institutes. So we suggest that future studies be conducted in a longer period of time and in pedagogical contexts of EFL other than language institutes. Moreover, teachers can be considered as participants as well to know their ideas and experiences of using Instagram or other mobile applications with the aim of teaching critical thinking.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

REFERENCES

- Ary, D., Jacobs, L. C., Sorenson Irvine, C. K., & Walker, D. A. (2019). *Introduction to research in education* (10th ed.). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Bagheri, M. (2015). Keep it accurate and diverse: Enhancing action recognition performance by ensemble learning. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops, Boston, MA, 22-29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPRW.2015.7301332>
- Carmichael, E., & Farrel, H. (2012). Evaluation of the effectiveness of online resources in developing student critical thinking: Review of literature and case study of a critical thinking online site. *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice*, 9(1).
- Corey, J. (2010). *Audio production and critical listening*. ISBN: Elsevier.
- Facione, N. (2013). CCTST test manual. (M. Kelly, Ed.), Insight Assessment. San Jose: Insight Assessment.
- Foo, S. Y. & Quek, C. L. (2019). Developing students' critical thinking through asynchronous online discussion: A literature review. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 7(2), 37-58.
- Halpern, D. F. (2014). *Thought and knowledge: An introduction to critical thinking* (5th ed.). New York and London: Psychology Press.
- Ku, Y. L. K. (2009). Assessing students' critical thinking performance: Urging for measurements using multi-response format. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 4, 70-76.
- Lopez-Perez, M. V., Perez-Lopez, M. C., & Rodriguez-Ariza, L. (2011). Blended learning in higher education: Students' perceptions and their relation to outcomes. *Computers & Education*, 56(3), 818-826. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.10.023>
- Moore, T. (2011). Critical thinking and disciplinary thinking: A continuing debate. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 30(3), 261-274. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2010.501328>

- Pnevmatikos, D., Christodoulou, P., &Georgiadou, T. (2019). Promoting critical thinking in higher education through the values and knowledge education (VaKE) method. *Studies in Higher Education, 44*(5).
- Saleh, S.E. (2019). Critical thinking as a 21st century skill: Conceptions, implementation, and challenges in the EFL classroom. *European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching, 4*(1), 1-16.
- Tabachnick, B. G., &Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics* (6th ed.). Boston: Pearson.
- Thompson, M. A. (2015). Using social media to learn and communicate: It is not about the Tweet. *American Society of Clinical Oncology Educational Book, 35*, 206–211. DOI: https://doi.org/10.14694/edbook_am.2015.35.206
- Ventura, M., Lai, E., &DiCerbo, K. (2017). *Skills for today: What we know about teaching and assessing critical thinking*. London: Pearson Education.
- Willingham, D. T. (2007). Critical thinking. *American Educator, 31*(3), 8-19.
- Zarrinabadi, N., Rezazadeh, M., &Chehrazi, A. (2021). The links between grammar learning strategies and language mindsets among L2 and L3 learners: Examining the role of and gender. *International Journal of Multilingualism, 1*, 49-71.

Author Information

Mahdi Zalani

Department of English Language and Linguistics, Faculty of Literature and Humanities, Razi University, Kermanshah, Iran.

Nouroddin Yousofi

Corresponding Author: Mahdi Zalani, Department of English Language and Linguistics, Faculty of Literature and Humanities, Razi University, Kermanshah, Iran.